

School counselors as agents of peace in the school: a systematic literature review

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ABSTRACT

Adolescence is a critical phase that can raise a problem, one of which is violence. This condition harms the dynamics of academic activities at school if they do not immediately find a solution. One party that has a central role in character development to suppress student violence is school counselors. This research is a systematic literature review that describes the counselor's role as an agent of peace whose primary focus is to build a culture of peace in the school environment. The results showed that counselors used two pillars of service to create a culture of peace in schools, namely peace guidance and peace counseling. This paper discusses operational descriptions for each of the posts to build a culture of peace in the school environment. This results should serve as a reference for school counselors in supporting their programs to reduce violence in schools. Besides, this study also recommends conducting further research to create a guidance and counseling program to reduce violence among adolescents in schools.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Peace is a new vision in the 21st century and one of Indonesia's pillars of character in education [1]. The conditions behind the emergence of this vision are the needs of the people of a country that not only requires material prosperity but also requires lasting peace and tranquility [2], [3]. People's need for peace indirectly challenges them to realize peace by living together and side by side in a calm, comfortable, minimally violent manner, with competitive conditions without contradiction and diversity without conflict [4]–[6]. People's expectations about living peacefully with the surrounding environment did not work as they should. Several studies have shown that the lack of peace in individuals correlates with violence [7]–[9]. Research in Indonesia shows that the level of aggressiveness tends to increase in an undesirable direction [10]–[12].

The violence that appears as a form of unrest has a negative impact, such as poor perceptions of the school climate [13] and academic performance [14]–[16]. The violence that occurs continuously encourages the development of cultural violence in a specific environment, including in schools. Cultural violence involves cultural aspects, regional symbols in religion and ideology, language and art, empirical science, and formal science that can justify and legitimize direct or structural violence [17]. The empirical study of the impact of non-peace on every human mind is the background to the importance of the counselor's role as an agent of

peace. Counselors have a central role in suppressing the rate of development of the problem of violence in students at school [18]. Various research results show that counselors can be agents of peace to create a culture of peace in the school environment [19], [20].

The importance of counselor's role as an agent of peace requires an intervention guide to build true peace in students. Counselors have a vital role as agents of peace, both in terms of guidance and counseling. Several studies have shown that counselors can implement guidance services to create student peace [10], [21], [22]. In addition, several studies have also shown that counselors can implement counseling services to build student peace [23], [24]. Patterns of guidance and counseling services that aim to develop peace can utilize local wisdom [25], such as the teachings of Markesot figures [26], KH Ahmad Dahlan [27], Gus Dur [28], and Mahatma Gandhi [29]. However, a number of previous studies have not provided a comprehensive explanation of the implementation of guidance and counseling services, including service strategies and characteristics of counselors as agents of peace.

This paper will comprehensively present the role of counselors as agents of peace in the school environment. The role of the counselor to build this peace will create a conducive student perception of the school climate. A conducive perception of the school climate can increase student involvement in achieving maximum academic achievement [15], [16], [30]. The results of the exposure to the findings of this study can be a reference for counselors to maximize their role in building and maintaining peace in the school environment.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Research design

This study aims to describe the role of schools' counselors as agents of peace in school settings. The study uses a qualitative research approach with a systematic literature review design to answer the research objectives. This study's systematic literature review research design used various primary literature sources from reputable academic journals with the keyword's peace educator, counselor as agent of peace, and counseling for peace.

2.2. Participants

This study uses articles with the keyword's peace educator, counselor for the agent of peace, and counseling for peace in 2018-2022. As a result, we got 93 articles with descriptions as presented in Table 1. The articles collected are used as a basis for describing the role of counselors as agents of peace.

We selected and identified articles from a total of 93 articles according to inclusive and exclusive criteria related to the research problem formulation. After reading and identifying the article's content as a whole, we found nine articles that fit the formulation of the research problem. Furthermore, in the outline, the process for reviewing articles in depth is described in Figure 1.

Table 1. Description of article identification in the academic journal

No	Search engine	Number of articles
1	ScienceDirect (SD)	10
2	Wiley Online Library (WOL)	12
3	Sage Journal (SJ)	15
4	Taylor and Francis Online (TFO)	26
5	PubMed (PM)	10
6	Google Scholar (GS)	20
	Total	93

2.3. Data collection tools

The data collection tool uses a search engine that can identify articles from reputable international journals related to the formulation of the problem. The keywords to search for articles are peace educator, peace counseling, and promoting peace with guidance and counseling. Search engines that identify articles in international databases in this study include the Wiley Online Library, ScienceDirect, Sage Journals, Taylor and Francis Online, PubMed, and Google Scholar.

This study also uses inclusive and exclusive criteria to select articles. The inclusive criteria for answering the problem formulation are focusing on the theoretical framework of implementing the characteristics of counselors who can promote peace; presenting the characteristics of peace educators; describing the role of guidance and counseling in promoting peace; writing articles in English; and the article is published by a reputable academic journal. We see the suitability of the inclusive criteria by reading and

understanding the entire article. Articles that do not meet the inclusion criteria and do not match the problem formulation are included in the category of exclusive criteria.

Figure 1. Study flow diagram

2.4. Data collection

The procedure for collecting research data includes several specific stages. First, we determine the research topic and formulate the problem. Second, assess search engines and compatible keywords to answer the problem formulation. Third, selecting articles, reducing data according to inclusion criteria, and synthesizing the article's content to answer the problem formulation. Based on these specific stages, this study can describe the role of counselors as agents of peace.

2.5. Data analysis

This study uses data extraction to analyze the data. This data analysis involves synthesizing the interpretation results of each article that falls into the category of inclusion criteria. The analysis of the interpretation of the research results led to new findings that describe the role of school counselors as agents of peace in schools. We extracted data from nine articles to answer the problem formulation. This extraction activity accommodates the production of research findings and conclusions. We identified nine articles by creating a table of article characteristics containing several components, namely the article's source, the type of research, research design, data collection tools, participants, country, results, and implications.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Identifying articles that match the inclusive criteria to answer the problem formulation results by nine articles. These articles formulate new research results to describe the role of counselors as agents of peace in schools. Table 2 presents a summary of the characteristics of the article based on the source of the article, type of research, research design, data collection tools, participants, country, results, and implications. These nine articles are the basis for describing the role of counselors as agents of peace in schools through guidance and counseling services.

Based on Table 1, this study can present a new finding about the efforts of counselors to create peace through guidance and counseling services. As an agent of peace, counselors must have peaceful states, attitude, and behavior consistent across their living spaces and life span (kK3). Characteristics of counselors to create peace based on empathy amid multiculturalism (kK1) and tolerance (kK2). These characteristics are essential for counselors' foothold in creating a culture of peace in pluralism.

As agents of peace, counselors must have strategies supporting their performance. The counselor's performance to create peace is done in two ways: peace guidance (jBK4) and peace counseling (jBK1, jBK3). Through peace guidance, counselors conduct psychoeducational efforts on ways to think peacefully when dealing with situations. Meanwhile, through peace counseling, the counselor raises awareness about the counselee's violent impulses and turns them into constructive thinking patterns to create self-peace for the counselee.

Counselors need to integrate peace guidance and peace counseling with local wisdom (jBK2). This local wisdom can give color and appeal to the counselee to internalize the values of peace in an aspect of local wisdom. In addition, peace guidance and peace counseling services use critical and sensitive communication patterns to social phenomena (SLBK1) and are based on the principle of diplomacy (SLBK2). Principles such as being critical, sensitive, and based on the principle of diplomacy are one of the characteristics of the counselee at this time. Thus, the mutual openness between the counselor and the counselee becomes one of the stimuli for the counselee in accepting the values of peace that they have not yet realized.

Table 2. Characteristics of articles analyzed

Source	Type	Design	Instrument	N	Results	Implication	Code
Bokhari and Ahmed	ES	QL	I	36	Promotion of peace by thinking critically and being sensitive to phenomena	Guidance and counseling strategy	sBK1
Zembylas and Loukaides	ES	QL	I	25	Promotion of peace with diplomatic strategy	Guidance and counseling strategy	sBK2
Badrkhani	ES	QL	I	5	A peace educator needs to emphasize the aspect of empathy amid multiculturalism	Counselor characteristics	kK1
Capistrano	NES	QL	N/A	N/A	Peace development through respect and tolerance	Counselor characteristics	kK2
Saputra <i>et al.</i>	ES	QN	Q	6	Peace counseling is effective in reducing aggressive behavior	Types of guidance and counseling services	jBK1
Supriyanto <i>et al.</i>	NES	QL	N/A	N/A	Prototype peace guidance and counseling based on local wisdom	Types of guidance and counseling services	jBK2
Saputra <i>et al.</i>	ES	QN	160	Q	Peace counseling model to reduce aggressive behavior	Types of guidance and counseling services	jBK3
Eliasa	NES	QL	N/A	N/A	The personality of the counselor who educates peace is peaceful states, attitude, and behavior that are consistent across one's living spaces and life span	Counselor characteristics	kK3
Purwadi <i>et al.</i>	ES	QN	210	Q	Peace guidance based on Marquesot to reduce aggressiveness	Types of guidance and counseling services	jBK4

Counselors as agents of peace play a role in building peace through the school setting. Guidance and counseling services are an intervention effort to build true peace. Figure 2 explains the counselor's role as an agent of the peace who contributes to creating true peace and it has three characteristics: tolerance, respect, and empathy. Two services implemented to build peace are peace guidance and peace counseling. Peace guidance focuses on efforts to suppress peace, while peace counseling focuses on efforts to replace thoughts that lead to the emergence of violence. The two services use a diplomatic strategy, sensitivity to phenomena, and a critical thinking strategy.

Counselors are professionals who can act as agents of peace. Through guidance and counseling services, counselors can play a role in creating true peace. Some works of literature refer to these services as peace guidance [21] and peace counseling [31]. The study's results using various literature state that peace guidance and peace counseling can utilize local wisdom to increase their effectiveness [25]. The peace scale can be used by counselors as a basis for implementing peace guidance and counseling [32]. Local wisdom does not have to come from a country because there are many other countries whose local wisdom can be adopted to develop peace guidance and peace counseling.

Professionals who have a role in creating true peace need a practical pattern of intervention that includes peace guidance and peace counseling [20], [33]. At the same time, not many studies describe the role of teachers as agents of peace, especially counselors. This article describes the role of counselors who

comprehensively provide guidance and counseling services to support the creation of true peace. The findings of this study can answer and contribute to scientific guidance and counseling that play a role in peace-building [34].

Figure 2. The pattern of the counselor's role as an agent of peace

The first counselor service whose goal is to create peace is peace guidance. The results stated that peace guidance is a counselor strategy to reduce aggressiveness [21]. Peace guidance in this study contains values such as humility, self-control, tolerance, forgiveness, focusing on self-strength, self-regulation, and behavioral regulation. Peace guidance is empirically proven to reduce student aggressiveness [22], [35], [36].

The second counselor service that aims to create peace is peace counseling. Several studies have shown that peace counseling is a strategy that can reduce students' aggressive behavior [24], [31]. The counseling model in this study involves several operational stages of behavior change, namely rationale of counseling, problem clarity, reflection of the phenomenon of violence, teaches alternative violent behavior, looking for different forms of violence, and evaluation and follow-up.

Local wisdom be an aspect that can support the success of peace guidance. The results show that counselors who use peace guidance based on Markesot's teachings can reduce students' aggressiveness [10]. The article describes the importance of Markesot's instructions in guiding peace, including humility, self-control, tolerance, forgiveness, self-strength oriented, self-regulation, and self-regulation. Other research has also formulated a prototype of peace guidance and counseling based on the value of local wisdom [25]. However, this research has not specifically determined the type of local wisdom. In addition, this research has not explained the success rate of peace guidance and counseling in reducing aggressiveness.

Several studies showed that several types of local wisdom can support the implementation of peace guidance and counseling. One study showed that the Markesot figure was one of the local wisdom that could teach peace [10], [26]. Markesot is a fictional character in Indonesia who is a manifestation of Emha Aiun Najib. In addition, Indonesian national figures such as KH Ahmad Dahlan [27] and Gus Dur [28] are also one of the local wisdom that teaches peace. However, from the results of these studies, there are still efforts to integrate guidance and counseling services to benefit developing student peace.

Indonesian figures are a form of local wisdom who teach peace on a war with international figures, such as Mahatma Gandhi. The world peace leader said that to achieve true peace, start with the children [29], [37]. Children can catch messages quickly and practice the concepts of peace in everyday life. Mahatma Gandhi recommended several values that children need to learn about peace, such as love for others, justice, non-violence, tolerance, and freedom of responsibility when faced with certain situations in life [29]. Teaching peace from childhood provides an essential principle that peace is a process requiring various parties' cooperation to make it happen [38].

Mahatma Gandhi brought the topic of love to create a wave of peace [39]. This love is the basis for someone to show their behavior in various areas, including, in this case, school life. Students who can lead and maximize love in their lives can then find solutions to various problems without violence. The results showed that love is a form of strong character that can support the emergence of students' subjective well-

being [40]. Education programs in Indonesia emphasize character development through character education, one of which is the love of peace [41].

The study research results showed that peace guidance and counseling can reduce student violence. The absence of violence in students triggers the emergence of true peace [9]. This true peace leads students to the emergence of well-being, a condition that they dream of when they are at school [42], [43]. With these conditions, students can perform self-actualization in all academic activities.

Counselors who apply the pattern of peace guidance and counseling services are a tangible manifestation of the implementation of peace education. Peace education is one educational model that aims to build peace in every human mind [44]. Indonesia is one of the countries with the potential to implement peace education, especially Indonesia is facing the challenges of global citizenship living in the 21st century, which allows conflicts between groups to emerge [5], [45]. The development of peace in thinking in children supports the success of education in minimizing conflicts and acts of violence that occur, especially in schools [46].

Counselors as agents of peace need to have characteristics such as tolerance and empathy amid multicultural currents. Tolerance is crucial in creating peace [47]–[49]. Likewise, empathy is also essential in building true peace [50], [51]. Counselors as agents of peace also need to have these characteristics before teaching students about the importance of tolerance in multicultural flows [52]. Herein lies the demands of the community's needs regarding the active role of counselors in building peace following the vision of 21st century guidance and counseling [53].

This study has limitations on empirical studies on effectiveness. Research in the form of a literature review on the role of counselors as agents of peace requires a follow-up to identify how successful the counselor is in building peace. This limitation is a stimulus for further research on implementing the counselor's role in building student peace. In addition, another limitation lies on the part of counselors in building peace which is focused on the implementation of guidance and counseling services. Guidance and counseling services have a comprehensive scope involving parents, stakeholders, and the community.

4. CONCLUSION

Violence is a problem of concern in a multicultural societies, including Indonesia. This violence arose as a result of non-peace in humans. The counselor is one of the professionals to support the achievement of the peace of society through schools. The counselor's efforts to create peace are by implementing peace guidance and counseling. Both services from these counselors use elements of local wisdom to increase their success. The results of this study should be one of the references for further research to develop peace guidance and counseling models that contain specific elements of local wisdom in various countries. In addition, it is necessary to study the peaceful patterns of Indonesian society as a basis for building a more comprehensive concept of peace guidance and counseling.

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